

SARS: analysis of recombinant ancestry, RBM composition and nucleotide repeat motifs suggests an unnatural origin

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Abstract

SARS is shown to have a recombinant ancestry comprised of a backbone from a Chinese/South East Asian lineage bat virus, and the Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) from a virus of African or European lineage. Aside from the geographical hurdle of such a union occurring naturally, the RBD incorporates additional substitutions and insertions that appear designed to enhance binding affinity non-specifically, disproportionately favoring residues that form strong hydrogen bonds and salt bridges. Few of these are conserved in related bat coronaviruses and there are additional indications that they may have been introduced artificially.

Introduction

SARS is presumed to be natural and of bat origin based largely on discoveries by the Wuhan Institute of Virology and China's Academy of Military Medical Science. However my recent work casts doubt on the validity of this evidence¹². The viruses WIV1, Rs3367, RsSHC014 and WIV16 may be artificial chimeras, not natural as was claimed. This assumption undermined, the origin of SARS must be considered an open question, and an artificial origin also considered.

When SARS emerged in late 2002, there were just two known coronaviruses able to infect and transmit between humans, OC43 and 229E. Though having shared ancestry with animal coronaviruses, these were thought to have diverged in relatively ancient times. They are thus well-adapted, endemic and have mild "common cold" symptoms. Today there are seven known human coronaviruses with the addition of SARS, HKU1, NL63, MERS and - most recently, SARS-CoV-2. Although factors like human encroachment on animal habitat, wildlife smuggling, environmental factors have been proposed as factors in this more frequent emergence, these don't seem unique to our times. In fact, human contact with wildlife is lower than ever due to rapid urbanization, particularly in China and South-East Asia. As is wildlife consumption, due to the massive reduction in poverty, and stigmatization of such practices.

Around the turn of the millennium, preceding the outbreak of SARS there were several scientific advances that enable an artificial emergence of novel coronaviruses. Researchers were interested in why coronavirus host range was limited, and what might drive host switching. This led to an understanding that the main driver of tropism is the spike protein, culminating in the first artificial chimera which could infect cells of a different species. Several groups published on new reverse genetic systems, which overcame a previous obstacle - the large size of the coronavirus genome.

Other important advances in generic genome engineering were related to nucleases, which recognize specific DNA sequences and cut the strands near that point. Most engineering techniques had relied on bacterial derived restriction enzymes which evolved to recognize palindromic sequences. However these are limited in that most are short sequences of 4-8 nucleotides which often occur too frequently to be of practical use. Although more than 3500 enzymes have been discovered, between them they only recognize some ~230 different sequences. There was interest in nucleases that could be engineered to recognize larger sequences, and which can be tailored to specific sequences. Zinc finger nucleases (ZFN) were perhaps the earliest practical solution, one still popular design was first described in 1995¹. Other solutions use meganucleases², inorganic chemical nucleases³, TALE nucleases, and CRISPR/Cas-9⁴.

Palindromes and inverted repeats retain their importance in techniques based on these nucleases. Mirror repeats may have significance in applications using RNA, rather than DNA, which some nucleases can also bind.

Ancestry of SARS

Backbone

There are two main lineages of SARS-related coronaviruses. One is centered in China and South East Asia, one is known to extend from Africa, through Europe, with discoveries to date as far apart as Rwanda, Russia, Bulgaria and the UK.

Figure 1 SNAP diagram comparing Rp3 to SARS in ORF1ab. The green line represents synonymous mutations, the red non-synonymous.

The closest sarbecov to SARS in much of the genome is Rp3⁵. Although this virus was discovered by the WIV, and I have doubts over the provenance of their viruses, I consider this one, sequenced in 2004, to be genuine. Comparing Rp3 to SARS there are ~200 non-synonymous mutations, and 800 synonymous a ratio of approximately 1:4.

Another sarbecov from the Chinese/S.E Asian lineage, discovered independently is HKU3. It is considerably more distant with ~1900 syn and ~380 non-syn, but a NS:S ratio of ~1:5 still indicates low selection pressure.

Figure 2 SNAP diagram of SARS vs HKU3. HKU3 are more distantly related than Rp3, however selection pressure is still low.

Comparing SARS to members of the Afro-European lineage shows they are far more distant. An example is Kenyan virus BtKY72, collected in 2007, which has almost 1500 non-synonymous and 3000 synonymous mutations between it and SARS. The NS:S ratio of 1:2 indicates much stronger selection pressure.

For a virus that emerged in Southern China, this is not unexpected. However the picture becomes more complex when looking at the spike. The spike of Rp3 has about 370 NS and 450 S mutations. The NS:S ratio is close to 1:1 and exceeds it for the hyper-variable part of the gene.

SARS Spike YP_009825051.1 vs Rp3 AAZ67052.1

It is overall a little closer to SARS, than the Afro-European lineage – but not by much.

SARS Spike YP_009825051.1 vs BtKY72 APO40579.1

A recently discovered virus from Vietnam, near the border with China RtVN-21-29 is far closer in the NTD of SARS Spike than is Rp3, and is similarly close in ORF1ab⁶, however it's provenance needs to be confirmed (this will be the subject of a future paper).

Figure 5 Nucleotide alignment near first putative recombination breakpoint. Bases where SARS agrees with all, and only with Chinese covs are shown in green, and with all Afro-European covs in orange. Others bases are less conserved within, or the same between, each lineage. Nucleotide numbering is from start of Spike gene.

Figure 6 Sequence alignment near second putative recombination breakpoint. Estimated to lie between 22992 and 23024.

One recent paper showed that Kenyan bat coronavirus BtKy72⁷, can bind *R. affinis* ACE2. Separate studies have showed that UK sarbecov RHGB07⁸, and Russian sarbecov Khosta-2⁹ can bind human ACE2, albeit sub-optimally. The Chinese lineage is not able to bind human or bat ACE2, but uses a different (unknown) receptor.

A possible fraud obfuscates the origin of SARS

WIV's Rp3 was initially shown to be unable to bind *R. pearsonii*'s ACE2 (let alone human ACE2). In 2008 WIV claimed they had wrongly identified the host, and its true host was *R. sinicus*¹⁰. They subsequently published ACE2 sequences purportedly belonging to *R. sinicus*, and showed SARS RBM could bind to that¹¹, so suggesting a possible evolution by recombination between an Rp3 like backbone, and an ACE2 binding sarbecov. In November 2013, WIV announced new viruses, WIV1, Rs3367 and RsSHC014. WIV1 and Rs3367 have an RBM very similar to SARS, without the deletion characteristic of Chinese coronaviruses. RsSHC014 has some curious additional homology to BM48-31, but again is without deletions. However I have previously shown that the claim these were found in nature is likely fraudulent¹², and they are perhaps artificial chimeras. Subsequent discoveries from WIV and other Chinese state and military institutions are also questionable.

It is also noteworthy that the breakpoints identified for SARS don't precisely align with those between WIV1/Rs3367/RsSHC014, further undermining a hypothesis there are naturally preferred breakpoint locations.

Figure 7 The breakpoints for WIV1/Rs3367/RsSHC014 identified previously by the author do not precisely align with those identified for SARS.

Figure 8 It is possible to identify breakpoints between WIV1/Rs3367/RsSHC014 precisely due to otherwise extremely high (>99.9%) nucleotide identity between them in most of the genome. These breakpoints in turn correspond almost exactly to the locations used in a previous experiment to make an artificial chimeric spike.

Structure and function of SARS RBM

Enrichment in tyrosine and hydrogen bonding residues

Even compared to the Afro-European lineage SARS RBM is enriched in the types of residues which are known to form strong bonds between proteins. Tyrosine (symbol: Y or Tyr) is particularly important to SARS' ACE2 binding, including several contact residues. The importance of tyrosine in protein interactions is also well known to genetic engineers. From Koide and Sidhu¹³:

“The physicochemical properties of tyrosine make it the amino acid that is most effective for mediating molecular recognition, and protein engineers have taken advantage of these characteristics to build tyrosine-rich protein binding sites that outperform natural proteins in terms of affinity and specificity”

Even compared to Afro-European sarbecovs, SARS is enriched in tyrosine. Towards the 3' end of the RBM, there are three Y residues which are largely conserved in all bat covs. Another Y is unique to the Chinese lineage, and one is unique to the Afro-European lineage. SARS giving it 5 Ys in this region, while the others have 3-4.

Figure 9 SARS has an extra 1- 2 tyrosine residues in the 3' of the RBM compared to both Chinese and Afro-European covs.

Upstream of the 5' of the RBM is a 4 amino acid motif YNYK that is conserved in all sarbecovs. Uniquely in SARS (among sarbecovs whose authenticity can be presumed), YNYK is repeated as an insert. This insert is in a critical position in the RBM. One of its Ys is a contact residue¹⁴, as are two more downstream¹⁴ (these are shown in bold: **YNYKYRY**). It is thus a major determinant of strong ACE2¹⁵ binding.

Figure 10 SARS RBM contains a motif YNYK that is nucleotide identical to the same motif upstream. It also has an extra tyrosine with a difficult combination of mutations needed to evolve it.

Although most bat coronaviruses contain 2-3 tyrosine residues at this site, spacing is important. The final tyrosine in this motif is unique to SARS. As the sequence most closely follows the European and African coronaviruses we might assume it had evolved from one of them. However the nucleotide sequence doesn't make this seem likely, with a minimum of two mutations needed, in first and second positions at that. It might more viably have evolved from a Chinese cov, with just a single mutation needed, but there is less homology around this.

RhGB02	aga	ctc	ttt	aga
BM48-3	agg	aga	ttc	aga
BtKy72	agg	ctt	ttt	aga
PRD-038	agg	ctt	ttt	aga
SARS	agg	tat	ctt	aga
HKU3-1	aga	tct	cat	cgc
Rp3	aga	tct	cat	cgc
Rm1	aga	tct	tac	aga

Figure 11 Nucleotide alignment shows SARS unique additional Y442 (blue) is formed by multiple nucleotide changes from the Afro-European sarbecovs.

Figure 12 Tyrosine is particularly important to the ACE2 binding of SARS, including six contact residues. Rendered from PDB 6CS2¹⁶.

Curious duplication of a palindromic motif

Natural evolution, perhaps involving multiple deletions, is one possible, though unlikely, explanation for the duplication of the YNYK motif, given bat sarbecovs have 2-3 tyrosine residues near the site.

However, is it also simply coincidence that the two YNYK sequences are identical over 15 nucleotides? A more parsimonious explanation may be needed.

Further mystery is added because within this 15nt is a repeated 6nt palindromic sequence TTATAA (or alternatively a 12nt palindrome TTATAATTATAA).

Figure 13 SARS contains 2 sequences YNYK encoded by 15 identical nucleotides. Within this sequence is a 12 nt palindromic sequence.

The 5' instance of the palindrome is conserved in two sequences collected in the UK¹⁷ (RhGB02 and RhGB03), and in two from Africa (BtKY72 and PRD-038). It is not present in Chinese coronaviruses, despite amino acid conservation.

SARS	g	t	t	g	t	t	a	a	t	t	a	a	t	t	g	c	c	a	g	a	t										
PRD-0038	g	t	t	g	t	t	a	a	t	t	a	a	t	t	g	c	c	a	g	a	t										
BtKY72	g	t	t	g	t	t	a	a	t	t	a	a	t	t	g	c	c	a	g	a	c										
RhGB02	g	t	t	g	t	t	a	a	t	t	a	a	t	t	g	c	c	t	g	a	t										
BM48	g	t	g	a	t	t	t	a	c	a	a	t	a	c	a	a	t	t	g	c	c	t	g	a	t						
Rm1	g	t	t	g	t	t	t	a	c	a	a	c	t	a	c	a	a	t	t	a	c	c	t	g	a	t					
HKU3	g	t	t	g	t	t	g	a	c	t	a	c	a	a	t	a	c	a	a	g	t	t	g	c	c	t	g	a	t		
Rp3	g	t	t	g	t	t	g	a	c	t	a	c	a	a	t	a	c	a	a	g	t	t	g	c	c	t	g	a	t		
RtVN29-21	g	t	c	a	t	t	g	c	a	g	a	c	t	a	c	a	a	t	t	a	a	a	c	t	a	c	c	t	g	a	t

Figure 14 the sequence around the 5' YNYK motif most closely resembles African covs, although two UK covs also conserve the palindrome (blue).

Again the sequences are better conserved in European bats and best of all in African sarbecovs, and worst in Chinese sarbecovs (excluding those discovered from 2013 and later, that are possibly fraudulent¹²).

It's also interesting to compare the sequence of SARS and SARS-CoV-2 at the 3' version of the site. SARS-CoV-2 doesn't conserve the 12nt palindrome of SARS-1, but remarkably, it has a 16nt palindrome which mostly overlaps.

Figure 15 Remarkably SARS-CoV-2 also has a palindrome at a not-quite overlapping location.

Of the genomes studied, excluding SARS (n=13) and SARS-CoV-2 (n=15), the average number of 12 nucleotide palindromes is 11, however SARS is alone in having two that are identical. The unusual occurrence was first noted by Chew et al, 2004¹⁸, although they didn't consider the functional importance of the amino acid sequence. The average occurrence of 16 nt or greater palindromes is 0.86. SARS-CoV-2 has 3, while SARS has one extraordinary 22 nt palindrome. This was also noted first by Chew et al, 2004¹⁸, who estimated that such an occurrence would be expected in around 1% of genomes of a similar size. More information on the frequency of similar palindromic sequences is in the supplementary materials.

Significance of palindromic and inverted repeat sequences in genetic engineering

Palindromes and inverted repeats have sequences which read the same on the forward and reverse strands of DNA. In palindromes the sequences overlap, while with inverted repeats they are separate. Both make good recognition sites for genetic engineering of DNA, many bacteria derived natural restriction enzymes evolved to recognize palindromic sequences. Most restriction enzymes recognize only short (4-8bp) pre-defined, sequences. Sequences of this size may naturally occur too frequently through the genome to be useful, or not in the right places, so further engineering steps are needed. Engineers have found other solutions, to recognize longer sequences of their own specification. CRISPR is the most recent, and perhaps easiest to use, however was not sufficiently developed before the SARS outbreak.

Zinc Finger Nucleases (ZFN) were more advanced, and more widely used at the time. A Zinc Finger Protein can bind to a DNA (and in some cases RNA) strand, each ZFP recognizing a 3-nucleotide sequence which can be customized. While 3nt is not enough to be useful, modular architectures are utilized based on assembling multiple 3nt fingers, sometimes in combination with the cleavage domain of a bacterial restriction enzyme (FokI is frequently used)¹⁹.

Figure 16 Typical ZFN architecture. Image from Urnov et al, 2011

Compared to the use of restriction enzymes, engineering individual zinc fingers to recognize a custom sequence is a non-trivial task, neither is assembling the modules. It is expedient when engineering to reuse where possible. A sequence such as TTA-TAA-TTA-TAA, being both palindromic and a repeat would require the customization of only 2 zinc finger templates, and these are themselves very similar differing in just one base.

However this is just one possibility. Inverted repeats and palindromes have roles in recombinases, transcription regulators and plasmids. Identifying specific engineering technique used is beyond the scope of this paper.

SARS RBM is enriched in salt bridge forming residues

Salt bridges are another strong bond formed optimally between acidic (D/E) and basic (R/K/H) amino acids. SARS has four of these residues that appear unique to it, and one R426 which it shares with RhGB02. However the nucleotide sequence between them at this site has very low homology. It is nonetheless a variable site surface exposed and under immune pressure. R426 has been shown to be very important in forming salt bridges and/or hydrogen bonds with more than one corresponding ACE2 residue²⁰.

Figure 17 SARS has several residues with potential to form salt bridges (R/K/E/D) that are unique or shared with few other bat coronaviruses.

Figure 18 Although RhGB02 has an Arginine in same position as R426, it is likely to have evolved independently as the sequence is poorly conserved otherwise.

SARS-CoV-2 Furin Cleavage Site flanking sequence

Upstream of the SARS-CoV-2 furin cleavage site insert (PRRA) is a length 15 mirror repeat:

Figure 19 Mirror repeat of length 15 upstream of the furin cleavage site insert

Within the mirror repeat is a 6nt direct repeat CAGACT-CAGACT, which is in-frame, encoding the QTQT amino acid sequence. Although this amino acid sequence is conserved in some putative SARS-CoV-2 related coronaviruses (the authenticity of these will be questioned in a future paper), the nucleotide sequence and repeat is unique to SARS-CoV-2. QTQT is encoded in other genomes most often as CAGACT-CAAAC. The unique encoding, combined with the FCS insert results in a region highly enriched in potential restriction sites.

Figure 20 Type IIS restriction sites encoded by the sequence near putative bat coronavirus RaTG13's S1/S2 junction. The recognition site is the same for all: GACTC.

Figure 21 Type IIS restriction sites encoded by nucleotide combinations within the highlighted range in SARS-CoV-2.

This sequence has been misidentified as palindromic in another paper²¹. This is a significant error as mirror repeats don't have the same implications for RNA secondary structure, not bringing matching complementary bases into close proximity.

Other significant palindromes and repeats

Length 22 palindrome in ORF3a

A 22-nt long palindrome in the ORF3a of SARS-1 was first identified by Chew et al, 2004²². They estimated the probability of a palindrome of this size occurring in a similar sized genome at around 1%. Like most authors, Chew et al, didn't consider potential genetic engineering applications, or that SARS-1 may have been unnatural. A search of betacoronavirus genomes identified only one other palindrome of length 22, in an equine coronavirus.

This palindrome is not conserved in SARS-CoV-2, however Ghosh et al identified a length 20 inverted repeat²³ in a similar, but non-overlapping position towards the 3' end of ORF3a. Ghosh et al also identified a second 18 nt palindrome very nearby in ORF3a, however this may not function properly as a unique restriction site as there is another (non-repeat) occurrence of the forward sequence in ORF1ab. Nonetheless it is interesting to find these rare sites in close proximity. A BamHI restriction site is also interesting, being relatively rare²⁴, and unique in each of these genomes.

There is otherwise a dearth of similar features in this part of the genome, even of smaller sizes.

Distribution of palindromes and repeat sequences

Ghosh et al programatically identified large palindromes, mirror repeats and inverted repeats and provide tables in their supplementary material²³. I mapped the distribution of all palindromes of size 12 or greater, mirror repeats of size 12 or greater, and inverted repeats of size 18 or greater, based on their results. I manually identified a handful of additional sites that seem significant, but were not identified in their analysis.

Sites predominately cluster in Spike, mostly in S1, and nsp3 of ORF1ab, particularly around PLPro and the nucleic acid binding domain.

SARS-CoV-1

Figure 22 Distribution of large palindromes (P), mirror repeats (M) and inverted repeats (IR) in SARS-1. The YNYK sequences are palindromes of length 12.

SARS-CoV-2 is enriched in mirror repeats compared to other sarbecovs, having 58, compared to an average of 41.5. There are 5 matching pairs of mirror repeats, compared to average of 1.5. Each seems to be located relatively close to its match.

More study is needed to understand whether the frequency and distribution of these features varies significantly from other viruses. Initial work shows that SARS and SARS-CoV-2 are outliers in some regards, but not to an extreme degree. Frequency tables comparing the related coronaviruses referenced in this paper are in the supplementary material.

Discussion

SARS is apparently formed of a recombination between a Chinese/SE Asian lineage backbone virus with the RBD region of Spike substituted with that of a European or African virus. The RBM has been enriched (compared to both lineages) with additional tyrosine residues and others that form strong bonds such as salt bridges and hydrogen bonds. This likely accounts for the broad host range of SARS. A duplicated amino acid motif YNYK near the RBM is unlikely to be natural given 15/15 nucleotide identity, and that it isn't conserved in bat sarbecovs.

Attempts have been made to provide a natural evolutionary explanation for these features, particularly by Wuhan Institute of Virology^{26 27 28}, and the Academy of Military Medical Sciences²⁹. I have recently proposed that these claim may be fraudulent¹². Excluding such sequences from analysis illuminates possible unnatural features of the subjects of interest.

It is only possible to speculate how SARS and SARS-CoV-2 may have been engineered, what techniques may have been applied, but some palindromic and repeat sequences are remarkable, and may be artifacts of engineering. More work needs to be done on understanding the relative frequency and conservation of such sites in natural bat coronaviruses. There is an additional problem in identifying which sequences are genuine¹². This paper is intended to provoke further investigation and discussion around this, and makes no claim to have dispositive answers.

Future work will look at other curious genomic features of SARS and SARS-CoV-2 and the zoonotic sequences purporting to support their natural evolution.

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